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Chord: A distributed Overlay Network Mechanism for Peer-to-Peer Systems

TUNAZZINA TAFANNUM^{1*}, SANJIDA AFRIN JISAN²

¹Department of Computer Science & Engineering, School of Science & Engineering, Southeast University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

²Department of Computer Science & Engineering, School of Science & Engineering, Southeast University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT

This research is based on “Chord: A distributed overlay network mechanism for Peer-to-Peer Systems”. The chord algorithm is implementation of logarithmic complexity for structured peer-to-peer network. An essential issue that goes up against peer-to-peer applications is the efficient area of the node that stores a suitable data item. For this issue, Chord provides support to fix it. Chord algorithm is best for designing Peer-to-Peer network and application. Chord is based on consistent hashing. It supports one operation which is Given a key, determines which node is responsible for storing the key value. We analyze the algorithm for both peer join and peer failure. When we analyze the algorithm it gives some insight into the behaviour of the system. This paper is mainly focused on how Chord is working for peer-to-peer networks.

Keywords

Peer-to-Peer, Chord, Peer joins, Peer failure, DNS, DHT, Consistent Hashing

Introduction

Now - a - days networking is the most important and common means to connect all over the universe. Overlay network (M.F.M Firdhous, 2011) is one of the most leading tools for internet research and development. An overlay network is built on top of one or more networks. An overlay network can also be explained as a logical network. It defines routing and service model for communication. This network can change properties in one or more areas of underlying network.

Peer-to-Peer (P2P) (S.Ayyasamy and S.N.Sivanandam, 2010) network is an overlay network. Peer-to-Peer is a decentralized network system. Here, client send a service request and the service complete the request. P2P network used for various applications Such as routing of network traffic, massive parallel computing

environments, distributed storage and many other functions. One of the best Peer-to-Peer network examples is internet. There are some P2P software programs which are Kaza, Gnutella, Tapestry and more. When connected to the network, P2P software give permission to search for files on other's computers. P2P network share their file and resourceful data. File sharing is easy and suitable.

Chord (Alaa Arabiyat, Sulieman and Mohammad F. 2013) is one of the best applicant for designing Peer-to-Peer network and application. Chord is a distributed lookup protocol. It has key identifier and node identifier. Both are uniformly distributed. Chord is suitable because of its simplicity, provable correctness. It has scalable node localization.

Distributed hash table (DHT) (CH.Sushma and D. navaneetha, 2013) is a decentralized table which provides a lookup service to a distributed system. It has (key, value) pairs. This system supports just one function. Chord is the standard example for Distributed hash table. In DHT system any given item can find quickly. The key value controls which node stores the value. For data storage it can also distribute responsibility.

Peer-to-Peer network:

Peer-to-peer (P2P) (S.Ayyasamy and S.N.Sivanandam, 2010) is a decentralized communications model in which each party has the same capabilities and either party can initiate a communication session. . The P2P network model allows each node to function as both a client and server. . The P2P network model allows each Node to function as both a client and server. The (client, server) model, in which the client makes a service request and the server fulfills the request properly.

P2P systems can be used to provide anonymized routing of network traffic, massive parallel computing environments, distributed storage and other functions. Most P2P programs are focused on media sharing and P2P is therefore often associated with software privacy and copyright violation. When music-sharing P2P applications like Napster appeared.

Overlay network:

Overlay networks (M.F.M Firdhous, 2011) run as independent virtual networks on top of another physical network. Most overlay networks run on top of the public network. Overlay networks also create several challenges and problems for us to do research. Nodes in the overlay can be thought of as being connected by virtual or logical links. For example, distributed systems such as peer-to-peer networks and client-server applications are overlay networks because their nodes run on top of the internet.

Distributed hash table:

Distributed hash table (DHT) (CH.Sushma and D. navaneetha, 2013) is a distributed memory approach, of which the single node can be expanded to the whole Internet. Each node is controlled by a part of the whole resource space. (Key, value) pairs are stored in a DHT. Any participating node can efficiently retrieve the value associated with a given key. It is decentralized mechanism for associating hash values keys with some kind of content. Each node maintains a routing table, and then the selective information can be transmitted through the routing table. A distributed hash table provides a fault tolerant storage on top of which is layered

an application such as file sharing, distributed backup. The main advantage of DHTs is their scalability. Responsibility for maintaining the mapping from keys to values is distributed among the nodes, in such a way that a change in the set of participants causes a minimal amount of disruption. This allows a DHT to scale to extremely large numbers of nodes and to handle continual node arrivals, departures, and failure. Finally we design a series of experiments to verify the effectiveness of the proposed algorithm.

Algorithm:

Chord:

Chord is an organized Peer-to-Peer (P2P) (S.Ayyasamy and S.N.Sivanandam, 2010) overlay network (M.F.M Firdhous, 2011). In chord protocol participating peers share resources as equal. One of the new proposal for building extensive internet application is chord. Chord is supposed one of the best candidates. Chord has ability to address some difficult problems. Statements such as the following are facts:

Load balance:

Hash function is used by Chord. It assigns keys to the nodes evenly. Native load balance of data items created these results on network nodes.

Decentralization:

Chord has higher capabilities and fully distributed. This makes Chord suitable for Peer-to-Peer applications.

Scalability: Size constant or logarithmic in the number of existing nodes in the network with each node keep only a small routing table. Using Chord can be applied very large system.

Availability:

The node keeping a key can always be setup because when the nodes newly joined as well as node failures Chord protocol necessarily renews its routing table.

Flexible naming:

The Chord key-space is exposed. This gives applications the flexibility to represent their own names to Chord keys according to some hashing function. Neither restriction nor control are expressed by the Chord system.

Consistent hashing:

Consistent hashing function is used by Chord to represent keys to its nodes. The consistent hash functions allocate network nodes (peers) and data keys an m-bit identifier. They are using SHA-1 as the base function. While a key identifier is created by hashing the data key, a peer's identifier is chosen by hashing the peer's IP address. The big length of the identifier m must be big enough. They are usually taken to be 128 bit or 160 bit. An identifier circle module 2^m as a logical ring. Key k is allocated to the first peer whose identifier is equal to or follows k in the identifier space. This peer is denoted by successor(k) and it's called the successor peer of key k. When a peer n joins the network, the ID of the joined node are equal or less than certain keys to maintain consistent hashing mapping. They were previously assigned to n's successor now need to be reassigned to n. In Chord ring all of its

assigned keys are reassigned to n's successor and it's become responsible for these keys when peer n leaves the ring.

Materials and methods

Scalable key location:

In the Chord ring each peer needs to know how to locate its successor peer on the identifier circle. An example is defined in the following figure:- For key 54 a lookup is applied by peer 8. For this key peer 8 run the find successor operation which returns the successor of that key, i.e. peer 56. Between peer 8 and peer 56 the query passes every peer on the ring.

In the (key, Node) ID space m is the number of bits. Each peer n keeps a routing table with up to m entries which is called the finger table. In this table the i th entry table at peer n contains the identity of the first peer s that succeeds n by at least 2^{i-1} on the identifier circle, i.e., $s = \text{successor}(n + 2^{i-1})$, where $1 \leq i \leq m$. The i th finger of peer n is peer s . The Chord identifier and the IP address of the relevant peer both include a finger table entry. The following figure shows the finger table of peer 8 and the first finger entry for this peer points to peer 14, as the first peer that succeeds $(8+20) \bmod 26=9$. The last finger of peer 8 points to peer 42, i.e., the first peer succeeds $(8+25) \bmod 26=40$. (Alaa Arabiyat, Sulieman and Mohammad F. Ababneh, 2013)

One operation supports by Chord protocol given a key, it represents the key onto a node. That node might be responsible for storing a value associated with the key, depending on the application using Chord. Chord uses consistent hashing when information is out of date Chord node requires information about $O(\log N)$ other nodes for efficient routing, but performance degrades gracefully. This is important in practice.

It is hard to maintain when nodes will join and leave arbitrarily and consistency of even $O(\log N)$. For maintaining this information Chord has a simple algorithm. (Ion Stoica et al. 2003)

Peer joins:

The successor pointers of some peers need to be changed when a peer joins the system. The correctness of look ups is not guaranteed so it is important that the successor pointers are up to date at any time. Stabilization protocol is used by Chord protocol. It is running periodically in the background to update the successor pointers. In Chord protocol each peer is aware of its successors. It is possible that a peer does not know its new successor when peers fail it has no chance to learn about it. Peers maintain a successor list of size r to avoid this situation. It contains the peer's first r successors. Suppose that peer failures occur with a probability p and the probability that every peer on the successor list will fail is p^r . The system more robust when r increases.

The DHash (Distributed Hash) layer has some features. It performs block fetches for the peer, distributes the blocks among the servers and cached maintains and replicated copies. A lookup service is provided by Chord-based DNS with host names as keys and IP addresses as values (Eng Keong Lua and Jon Crowcroft. 2004). Each node maintain finger table .entity I in the finger table of n is the first node that succeeds or equals $n+2^i-1$. An item identified by id stored on the successor node of id .

Assume an identifier space (0-8) and node n_1 :(1) join. All entities in its finger table are initialized to itself. (Ion Stoica et al.2003). Now we can see the structure of node join n_1 .

Fig (a): Node join n_1 (1)

Now node 2 joins in this figure generally. Then we can see the result below

Fig (b): Node join n2 (2)

After that we join two nodes n3 :(0) and n4 :(6) in this architecture. Now we can see the figure.

Peer failure:

When the peers fail, it is possible that a peer does not know its new successors and it has no change to learn about it. Avoid this situation peers maintain a successor list of size r which contains the first r successors. When the successor peer does not respond the peer try to contact the next peer on its successor .This procedure make it easy for key replication, instead of storing key k at only successor kit is replicated on the r successor of k. In this way if successor fails, the other successor peers are still to response the answering for looking up key k. A list of successor using and applying replication of data items among them increase the toughness against very high degrees of node dynamics. (Alaa, Sulieman and Mohammad F. 2013)

Related work:

Three features that distinguish Chord from many other Peer-to-Peer lookup protocols its simplicity, provab correctness, and provable performance.

To clarify comparisons with related work, we will assume in this section a Chord-based application that maps keys onto values. A value can be an address, a document, or an arbitrary data item. A Chord-based application would store and find each value at the node to which the value’s key maps.

DNS: DNS provides a lookup service, with host names as keys and IP addresses (and other host information) as values. Chord could provide the same service by hashing each host name to a key (R. Cox, A. Muthitacharoen, and R. Morris. 2002). Chord-based DNS would require no special servers, while ordinary DNS relies on a set of special root servers. DNS requires manual management of the routing information that allows clients to navigate the name server hierarchy; Chord automatically maintains the correctness of the analogous routing information. DNS only works well when host names are structured to reflect administrative boundaries; Chord imposes no naming structure. DNS is specialized to the task of finding named hosts or services, while Chord can also be used to find data objects that are not tied to particular machines.

The Freenet: Freenet Peer-to-Peer storage system (I. Clarke, 1999), (I. Clarke, Sandberg, Wiley, and Hong. 2000), like Chord, is decentralized and symmetric and automatically adapts when hosts leave and join. Freenet does not assign responsibility for documents to specific servers; instead, its look ups take the form of searches for cached copies. This allows Freenet to provide a degree of anonymity, but prevents it from guaranteeing retrieval of existing documents or from providing low bounds on retrieval costs. Chord does not provide anonymity, but its lookup operation runs in predictable time and always results in success or definitive failure.

The Globe system: Globe system (A. Bakker et al. 2000) has a wide-area location service to map object identifiers to the locations of moving objects. Globe arranges the Internet as a hierarchy of geographical, topological, or administrative domains, effectively constructing a static world-wide search tree, much like DNS. Information about an object is stored in a particular leaf domain, and pointer caches provide search shortcuts (M. van Steen, F. Hauck, G. Ballintijn, and A. Tanenbaum, 1998). The Globe system handles high load on the logical root by partitioning objects among multiple physical root servers using hash-like techniques. Chord performs this hash function well enough that it can achieve scalability without also involving any hierarchy, though Chord does not exploit network locality as well as Globe.

The Distributed data location: Distributed data location protocol developed by Plaxton et al. (C. Plaxton, R. Rajaraman, and A. Richa, 1997) is perhaps the closest algorithm to the Chord protocol. The Tapestry lookup protocol (B. Zhao, J. Kubiawicz, and A. Joseph, 2001), used in Ocean Store (J. Kubiawicz et al. 2000), is a variant of the Plaxton algorithm. Like Chord, it guarantees that queries make no more than a logarithmic number of hops and that keys are well balanced. The Plaxton protocol's main advantage over Chord is that it ensures, subject to assumptions about network topology, that queries never travel further in network distance than the node where the key is stored. Chord, on the other hand, is substantially less complicated and handles concurrent node joins and failures well. Pastry (A. Rowstron and P. Druschel. 2001) is a prefix-based lookup protocol that has properties similar to Chord. Like Tapestry, Pastry takes into account network topology to reduce the routing latency. However, Pastry achieves this at the cost of a more elaborated join protocol which initializes the routing table of the new node by using the information from nodes along the path traversed by the join message.

Napster and Gnutella: Napster (Napster. 2014) and Gnutella (Gnutella. 2014) provide a lookup operation to find data in a distributed set of peers. They search based on user-supplied keywords, while Chord looks up data with unique identifiers. Use of keyword search presents difficulties in both systems. Napster uses a central index, resulting in a single point of failure. Gnutella floods each query over the whole system, so its communication and processing costs are high in large systems.

Chord has been used as a basis for a number of subsequent research projects. The Chord File System (CFS) stores file and metadata in a Peer-to-Peer system, using Chord to locate storage blocks (F. Dabek, F. Kaashoek, D. R. Karger, R. Morris, and I. Stoica. 2001). New analysis techniques have shown that

Chord's stabilization algorithms (with minor modifications) maintain good lookup performance despite continuous failure and joining of nodes (D. Liben-Nowell, H. Balakrishnan, and D. R. Karger, 2002). Chord has been evaluated as a tool to serve DNS (R. Cox, Muthitacharoen, and R. Morris. 2002) and to maintain a distributed public key database for secure name resolution (S. Ajmani, Clarke, C.-H. and S. Richman. 2002).

Analysis of chord:

Our analysis above gives some insight into the behavior of the Chord system, but is inadequate in practice. The theorems proven above assume that the Chord ring starts in a stable state and then experiences joins or failures. In practice, a Chord ring will never be in a stable state; instead, joins and departures will occur continuously, interleaved with the stabilization algorithm. The ring will not have time to stabilize before new changes happen. The Chord algorithms can be analyzed in this more general setting. Other work shows that if the stabilization protocols run at a certain rate (dependent on the rate at which nodes join and fail) then the Chord ring remains continuously in an "almost stable" state in which look ups are fast and correct. (LIBEN-NOWELL, D., BALAKRISHNAN, H., AND KARGER, D. R. 2002)

We are analyzing some structured peer to peer overlay networks. There are CAN, Chord and tapestry. CAN (Content Addressable Network) is fully decentralized and distributed hash table functionality on the internet-like scale. The architectural design of a CAN is multi-dimensional and Cartesian coordinate space. Key, value pairs to map a point P in the coordinate space using the uniform hash function. There are different types of dimension include in this network. The routing performance of CAN is $O(d \cdot N^{1/d})$. The routing state and peer join or leave depend on $2d$. Security of CAN is very low. Suffers from man-in-middle and Trojan attacks. CAN is more reliable because failure of peers will not cause wide network failure. There present multiple peers responsible for each data item. On failures, application retries. (Eng Keong Lua, Jon Crowcroft, Marcelo Pias, Ravi Sharma and Steven Lim. 2004)

Chord is a protocol and algorithm which are used to peer to peer distributed hash table. Chord is fully decentralized and distributed hash table functionality on internet-like-scale. Chord is one of the four original distributed hash table protocols. There are CAN, tapestry and pastry. The architectural design of a chord is

unidirectional and circular node ID space. The lookup protocol of chord is matching key and node ID. The System parameter found to be the N numbers of peers in the network. Time complexity of chord algorithm is $O(\log N)$. The routing state is $\log_B N$. Peer join or leave easily count by $(\log N)^2$ formula. Security level of chord is very low and suffers from man-in-middle and Trojan attacks. Chord algorithm is more reliable because failure of peers will not cause network-wide failure. Replicate data on multiple consecutive peers. On failures, application retries. (Eng Keong Lua, Jon Crowcroft, Marcelo Pias, Ravi Sharma and Steven Lim. 2004)

Tapestry is one of the structured peer to peer overlay network which is fully decentralize, efficient, scalable, self-repairing, location-aware routing to nearby resources. It provides a distributed hash table, routing and multi-casting infrastructure for distributed hash applications. Tapestry allows object distribution, determination according to the needs of a given application as same as allows applications to implement multi-casting overlay network. The lookup protocol of tapestry is matching key and node ID .The system parameter found to be the N number of peers in network B-base of the chosen peer identifier. The routing performance is $O(\log_B N)$ and the routing state is $(\log_B N)$. Formula used to be found the peers join or peer leave. The security level of tapestry is very low and suffers from man-in-middle and Trojan attacks. Tapestry is more reliable because failure of peers will not cause network-wide failure. Replicate data across multiple peers. Keep track of multiple paths to each peer. Tapestry was developed by Ben Y. Zhao, Ling Huang, Jeremy Stribling, Sean C. Rhea, Anthony D. Joseph and John D. Kubiawicz. (Eng Keong Lua, Jon Crowcroft, Marcelo Pias, Ravi Sharma and Steven Lim. 2004)

According to Chord protocol of P2P network, entries in the routing table are placed at a long distances that are all powers of 2 and only cover half of the identifier space. Therefore, an improved Chord routing algorithm is proposed. The algorithm presents a new routing table structure formula, increases entries distribution density, and extends routing searching coverage areas. Performance analysis and simulation experiments show that improved algorithm reduces the average lookup path length and gets higher efficiency. The peer to peer overlay network is best suited depends on the application and its required functionalities, performance metrics for example content distribution, scalability, network routing performance, file sharing, location service etc. All of this system is being applied to the multi-player game, ad-hoc services, sharing of music, provisioning of mobile electronics address book, and the distribution of workloads of mirrored websites.

Comparison of various structured P2P overlay network:

Algorithm	Structured P2P overlay network Comparisons		
Taxonomy	CAN	Chord	Tapestry
Decentralization	DHT functionality on internet-like scale		

Architecture	Multi-dimensional ID coordinate space	Uni-directional and circular node ID space	Plaxton-style global mesh network
Lookup protocol	Key, value pairs to map a point P in the coordinate space using uniform hash function	Matching key and node ID	Matching suffix in node ID
System parameters	N-number of peers in network-number of dimensions	N-number of peers in network	N-number of peers in network B-base of the chosen peer identifier
Routing performance	$O(d.N^{1/2})$	$O(\log N)$	$O(\log_B N)$
Routing state	2d	$\log N$	$\log_B N$
Peer join/leave	2d	$(\log N)^2$	$\log_B N$
Security	Low level, suffers from man-in-middle and Trojan attacks.		

Table: Comparison of various structured P2P overlay network

Conclusion

We close our analysis with thoughts on some decision as follow as:

It would be useful to provide a quantitative evaluation on P2P overlay application and internet topology matching and the scalability of P2P overlay application by the efficient use of the underlying physical network resources.

Proximity in P2P overlay routing is an important factor in the routing decision for P2P overlay network. There are on-going researches in this area based on mapping the peers into coordinate-based space.

Application of Peer-to-peer overlay networking models in mobile and ad-hoc wireless network because of their similar features, such as peer-to-peer routing, self-organizing. It would allow mobile peers to have optimized flow control, proximity-aware, load balancing, proximity-aware. The future of P2P overlay network

inexorably linked to the take-up and subsequent commercial success of P2P overlay computing, personal area, ad-hoc networking and networking file-sharing (J. Li, J. Jannotti, D. D. Couto, D. R. Karger, and R. Morris. 2000).

We accept that Chord will be an important component for peer-to-peer, large-scale dispersed applications such as cooperative file sharing, time-shared accessible capacity frameworks, distributed indices for archive and benefit revelation, and large-scale distributed computing stages.

Future work:

Different kinds of test bed (for example MITRON, BibTeX, vBET) are available to analyze the performance of CHORD. Our future plan is to make a comparative study of among different CHORD versions on a particular test bed.

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